

required for octahedral complexes of Ni^{II}. The calculated values for 10 *Dq* and *B* are 9 249 and 944 cm⁻¹ respectively.

Electronic spectra (in DMF) of the Co^{II} complex display three bands around 7 950, 16 250 and 19 200 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to the spin-allowed transitions, ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{2g}(F) (ν₁), ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴A_{2g}(F) (ν₂) and ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{1g}(F) (ν₃) respectively. The appearance of these bands suggests octahedral environment⁶ around Co^{II}. This stereochemistry of the Co^{II} complex is supported by the value of ν₂/ν₁ (2.05) which lies between 1.8 and 2.2, obtained for octahedral complexes. The values for 10 *Dq* and *B* are 9 310 and 970 cm⁻¹ respectively.

The ν_{NH} band (3 390 cm⁻¹) in the ir spectrum of 3-(dimethylaminomethyl)indole is not traceable in the spectra of the complexes, indicating the deprotonation and subsequent formation of metal-nitrogen bonding. A medium band observed at 1 150 cm⁻¹ (C-N) of aliphatic t-amine in the above ligand appeared at ~1 110 cm⁻¹ in the complexes, which is suggestive of the coordination of nitrogen atom of C-N with the metal.

The ir spectrum of veratraldehyde oxime showed a strong band at ~3 300 cm⁻¹ and a medium one at 3 200 cm⁻¹, characteristic of symmetric and anti-symmetric stretching vibrations of OH in N-OH group⁷. These bands remain unaltered in the spectra of the complexes, showing the non-involvement of this group in complexation. A sharp band at 1 660 cm⁻¹ (C=N) of the oxime group⁸ shows a negative shift of 20–25 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes, which shows the participation of the azomethine nitrogen in complex formation. The symmetrical stretching band at 1 045 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C) gets shifted to lower frequency region (1 020–1 015 cm⁻¹) in the complexes, which clearly shows that the oxygen atom of the methoxy groups also takes part in chelation. Thus azomethine nitrogen and oxygen atom of the methoxy groups are the coordination sites in this ligand.

The non-ligand bands at ~500–520 and 400–410 cm⁻¹ may be due to ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} respectively. The low frequency band at 230–225 cm⁻¹ in the complexes, is tentatively assigned to stretching vibration of metal linked to bridged halogen. Because the complexes are non-electrolytic in nature, sixth coordination position of metal is occupied by chlorine atom.

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Synthesis and Characterisation of New Mixed Azomethyne Schiff Base Complexes of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) and their Pyridine Adducts involving β-Diketones as Ligands

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METAL complexes of symmetrical azomethynes (imine complexes) have been widely studied¹.

During recent years a few complexes of mixed azomethynes have also been reported². In the present investigation new types of mixed ligand imine Schiff base complexes of the type MLL'.2H₂O, where, M=Co^{II}, Ni^{II} or Cu^{II}; L=acetylacetonimine, L'=benzoylacetonimine or 1,3-diphenyl-3-iminepropen-1-ol or L=benzoylacetonimine and L'=1,3-diphenyl-3-iminepropen-1-ol have been synthesised. The pyridine adducts of the mixed imine Schiff base complexes have also been prepared. The relative stability of the complexes have been described by thermogravimetric studies.

Experimental

Acetylacetone, benzoylacetonimine, dibenzoylmethane (Fluka), pyridine, cupric nitrate, nickel nitrate and cobalt nitrate hydrated were of A.R. grade. Ethanol, chloroform and benzene were purified by distillation before use.

Preparation of imine Schiff base complexes: To the cobalt, nickel or copper nitrate aqueous solution (0.2 mol) an excess of liquor ammonia was added till the hydroxide formed and dissolved resulting in the formation of metalamine complex. To it was added an alcoholic solution (0.2 mol) of acetylacetone and benzoylacetonimine or dibenzoylmethane, or benzoylacetonimine and dibenzoylmethane so that the metal and the two ligands were in 1 : 1 : 1 ratio. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 24 h in case of nickel compounds and 2 h for cobalt and copper compounds with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was then poured on an evaporating dish where the solid complexes were obtained immediately in case of cobalt and copper compounds, while in case of nickel the solid was obtained after 0.5 h. The resulting crystalline solid was washed with water and ethanol and air-dried.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Decomp. temp. from DTG curve (°C)	Analysis % :		μ_{eff} B.M.**
		N	Metal	
[(ACACimine, BZACimine)(H ₂ O)]CoII	235	8.02 (7.94)	16.38 (16.71)	4.58
[(ACACimine, DBMimine)(H ₂ O) ₂]CoII	318	6.55 (6.74)	14.57 (14.20)	4.55
[(BZACimine, DBMimine)(H ₂ O) ₂]CoII	254	5.88 (5.87)	12.80 (12.35)	5.27
[(ACACimine, BZACimine)(Py) ₂]CoII	234	12.11 (11.79)	12.02 (12.40)	5.00
[(ACACimine, DBMimine)(Py) ₂]CoII	305	10.55 (10.42)	11.00 (10.97)	4.90
[(BZACimine, DBMimine)(Py) ₂]CoII	247	9.63 (9.35)	9.55 (9.84)	4.83
[(ACACimine, BZACimine)(H ₂ O) ₂]NiII	409	8.12 (7.94)	17.14 (16.64)	3.00
[(ACACimine, DBMimine)(H ₂ O) ₂]NiII	353	7.01 (6.75)	13.97 (14.15)	3.15
[(BZACimine, DBMimine)(H ₂ O) ₂]NiII	340	5.98 (5.87)	12.52 (12.31)	2.91
[(ACACimine, BZACimine)(Py) ₂]NiII	182	12.00 (11.79)	12.55 (12.36)	2.88
[(ACACimine, DBMimine)(Py) ₂]NiII	335	10.55 (10.43)	11.12 (10.93)	3.10
[(BZACimine, DBMimine)(Py) ₂]NiII	212	9.48 (9.35)	10.00 (9.80)	3.28
[(ACACimine, BZACimine)]CuII	257	9.26 (8.70)	19.37 (19.76)	1.88
[(ACACimine, DBMimine)]CuII	332	7.55 (7.30)	16.39 (16.56)	1.78
[(BZACimine, DBMimine)]CuII	310	6.15 (6.28)	14.42 (14.26)	1.89

* (ACACimine) = Acetylacetonimine (C₈H₉ON) anion, (BZACimine) = benzoylacetonimine (C₁₀H₁₀ON) anion, (DBMimine) = dibenzoylmethanimine (C₁₅H₁₂ON) anion, Py = Pyridine - (C₅H₅N) ** At 300 K

Preparation of pyridine adduct: To a solution of cobalt or nickel compound prepared above (0.2 mol) in ethanol (20 cm³) was added pyridine (0.2 mol) in benzene solution (20 cm³). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h with constant stirring. On evaporating the solvent, the resulting coloured crystalline solid was air-dried.

In order to characterise and determine the structures of the complexes, elemental analysis, tlc, magnetic, conductance, TGA and visible and ir spectral studies were undertaken.

Results and Discussion

The azomethyne bifunctional mixed Schiff base complexes are very soluble in polar solvents like DMF and DMSO and also fairly soluble in chloroform. Molar conductivity values ($\Lambda = 0.04 - 0.003 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ in chloroform) revealed that all the complexes are nonconducting and are, therefore, neutral non-ionic complexes.¹

The analytical data (Table 1) correspond to the formula (MLL')₂X where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}; X = H₂O, Py and (CuLL') where HL = acetylacetonimine and HL' = benzoylacetonimine or dibenzoylmethanimine or HL = benzoylacetonimine and HL' = dibenzoylmethanimine.

Doraswami and Bhattacharya³ reported that when metalamine was treated with one equivalent

each of acetylacetonimine and salicylaldehyde, only aldehyde molecule is condensed with ammonia and acetylacetonimine remain as it is in the mixed ligand complex. It has been observed in present studies that when metalamine was treated with two different β -diketones, both the molecules of β -diketonimine undergo condensation with ammonia and form mixed azomethyne Schiff base complex. Tlc analysis shows the compounds to be pure.

The mixed azomethyne cobalt(II) complexes and their pyridine adducts are orange to brown with magnetic moments in the range 4.72–5.25 B.M. that is, they have very high orbital contributions. This is attributed to the three-fold orbital degeneracy of the ⁴T_{1g} ground state. The electronic spectra display a band at 11 000–17 000 cm⁻¹ with an associated shoulder at 17 857–20 000 cm⁻¹. There is an increase in optical density beyond 10 526 cm⁻¹, which indicates that there may be a third band or shoulder near 9 500 cm⁻¹. These spectra are consistent with high-spin six-coordinate cobalt(II), which give rise to three transitions⁴, ν_1 (⁴T_{2g} ← ⁴T_{1g}) at 8 000–10 000, ν_2 (⁴A_{2g} ← ⁴T_{1g}) at 11 000–17 000 and ν_3 (⁴T_{1g(b)} ← ⁴T_{1g}) at 18 000–26 000 cm⁻¹.

The copper(II) mixed azomethyne Schiff base complexes are paramagnetic having magnetic moment (1.88 B.M.) corresponding to one unpaired electron. The visible spectra show a broad band at

16 667 or 15 625 cm^{-1} which can often be resolved into at least three components, which agree with square-planar structure of copper(II) complexes.

The magnetic moment values of the nickel(II) azomethyne Schiff base complexes and their pyridine adducts are in the range 2.91–3.15 B.M. These complexes are green and their spectra are similar and characteristic of six-coordinate nickel(II), displaying the ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 transitions defined by the bands at 10 640–11 500, 16 666–18 500 and 22 900–25 000 cm^{-1} , respectively. The observed ν_2/ν_1 ratio values (1.56–1.60) fall well in the range of an octahedral structure.

In the ir spectra, no broad band appears near 2 700 cm^{-1} indicating that H-bonded OH hydrogen of both the β -diketones get dissociated after complexation. The two medium bands at 3 040 and 2 860–2 980 cm^{-1} correspond to C–H stretching of phenyl and methyl group respectively. All the mixed azomethyne and their pyridine adduct complexes show a band at 1 590–1 600 cm^{-1} (C=N) which confirms that both the β -diketone molecules condensed with ammonia in presence of metal ion and form amine Schiff base complexes. In all the mixed β -diketonamine Schiff base complexes, the strong band at 1 560 cm^{-1} can be attributed to the resonance between C–O–M and C=N...M links. In all these compounds a second band appears near 1 505 cm^{-1} , which can be attributed to the C=C link, same as reported by Bellamy and Branch⁵. The complexes of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) show a broad band at 3 600–3 400 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of coordinated water molecules⁶. The octahedral geometry of the complexes accounts for the association of two water molecules with the metal ion. While in pyridine adducts, this band disappeared. There is also a medium band at 3 320 cm^{-1} corresponding to NH stretching frequency. In many compounds this band is very weak due to a broad band that appears upto 3 300 cm^{-1} . Therefore, it is very difficult to distinguish OH and NH absorption bands.

In order to determine the thermal stability and the number of water molecules associated with the mixed amine Schiff base metal chelates the thermogravimetric analysis was carried out. DTG-thermogram for the copper(II) chelates reveals no weight-loss upto 200° indicating that there is no water of crystallisation or coordinated water present in the compounds. The nickel(II) chelates lost 6.5–8.5% of their weight at 50–200°, which corresponds to two water molecules. The weight-loss appearing after 120° indicates the presence of coordinated water in the complex. In the cobalt(II) chelates there is a weight-loss of about 3.0–3.5% below 100°, indicating the presence of water of crystallisation (absorbed water). The weight-loss of 7.0–8.0% upto 170° in the mixed imine cobalt(II) chelates indicates the presence of coordinated water molecules. While the thermogram of the pyridine adducts of the cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes show no loss upto 150°. The thermal stability order: $\text{Ni}^{II} > \text{Cu}^{II}$

Co^{II} was derived from the decomposition temperature obtained from DTG curves.

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Chromium(III) and Iron(III) Complexes of Isonitrosoketone Thiosemicarbazones

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THE metal complexes derived from thiosemicarbazones of diacetyl monoxime¹ and α -oximinobenzoylacetonilide² constitute an important class of antineoplastic agents endowed with interesting spectral features. Therefore, we ventured to synthesise the metal complexes of the related ligands, i.e. isonitrosoacetophenone thiosemicarbazone and its 4-chloroderivative and to characterise them with the aid of chemical and physicochemical methods of analysis.

Experimental

Isonitroso/4-chloroisonitrosoacetophenone was prepared³ and then condensed with thiosemicarbazide⁴ to obtain pure samples of the ligands.

A mixture of hot ethanolic solutions of $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (25 cm^3 , 0.01 mol) and the ligand (25 cm^3 , 0.02 mol) was refluxed on a water-bath for about 4 h. On cooling and simultaneous trituration with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) it yielded a brown amorphous solid, which was washed with ethanol-petroleum ether mixture (1 : 1, v/v) and dried over P_2O_5 under reduced pressure, (70%).

CrCl_3 was converted to $\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_3/\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_3$ by metathesis and the latter was used to synthesise the thiocyanate/cyanide complexes.

Iron(III) complexes were prepared by adopting the same procedure as described above using FeCl_3